

A REVIEW OF THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGY ON STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOME

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Abstract

This paper analysed how learning outcome is influenced by the effective use of technology. Instructional tools for effective teaching and learning were x-rayed. First among them is flipped classroom which allows learners to have a foreknowledge of the contents. Online/e-learning as a technological tool, was also discussed- via e-learning, distance learning becomes effective. It provides an opportunity for students to have a full grasp of content available to others on the conventional platform. Further to that, courses which require vivid outlooks via study trips can be taught using virtual and augmented realities (VR and AR). It was concluded that students' capacity for critical and creative thought would be enhanced by the use of technology in the teaching and learning process. It was recommended that schools should adopt the usage of technology in the teaching and learning process.

Keywords: e-learning, Distance Learning, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality.

Introduction

When a learner participates in an educational programme, course, or activity, the expertise, skills, or competencies that they are supposed to acquire or exhibit are referred to as learning outcomes. Learning outcomes are formed and moulded by a model, in other words, to enhance learning results, the preferred pattern is the learning model. This model is determined by the facilitator who could be the teacher or lecturer (Welerubun, Wambrauw, Jeni, Wolo & Damopolii, 2022). In the same vein, Saihu (2020) averred that how students experience and interpret the learning process, determines whether learning goals and outcomes are successfully attained or not. He proceeded by explaining the learning outcome to be a student-learning approach which is one of the benchmarks of success in the world of education. Learning outcomes can be described as the outcomes derived from the activities that were conducted among the students.

Instructional designers and teachers use learning outcomes as a guide. Educators can concentrate their educational efforts on the most important abilities, expertise, and knowledge by using learning outcomes. This guarantees that teaching time is effectively allocated, focusing on the most crucial elements of the curriculum- also, assessments are developed with learning outcomes in mind, ensuring that they support the objectives of education.

Similarly, the evaluation of an educational programme's overall efficacy is based on its learning outcomes. Establishing specific goals allows institutions to assess if students are meeting the desired results and make informed choices for improving the programme. Furthermore, accrediting bodies, businesses, parents, students, and other stakeholders want educational programmes to meet certain standards, which can be ensured by learning outcomes. The learning outcome is a success through the adoption of contextual teaching and learning (CTL) Ruto, Mema, Nduru & Ota (2023), which is made seamless through technology. With technology, learning becomes contextual and practical which is the outcome that proffers solutions to societal problems and challenges.

Digital technologies are a potent tool that can enhance education in several ways, which include making it simpler for teachers to create lesson plans and offering fresh approaches to teaching and learning. In other words, digital technology helps teachers create content for lesson delivery, which in turn helps in effective and seamless teaching and learning processes Haleem, Javaid, Qadri & Suman (2022). They further opined that students who learn digitally are more creative and feel like they have succeeded, which motivates them to learn more by thinking beyond the box of conventional methods. Also, a plethora of instructional tools, including clips, virtual classes, and e-books, are available to students.

Flipped Classroom, and Technological Tool for Improving Learning Outcome

A “flipped classroom” is a teaching model where “that which is traditionally done in class is now done at home, and that which is traditionally done as homework is now completed in class” (Bergmann & Samn, 2012). While students have taken time to study the course materials at home via online platforms, main class time serves as enrichment time. This system makes learners intuitive, reflective, independent, and creative in their learning.

Technology makes it easy for students across the world to acquire certifications through online courses, hence, helping to reach out to students across the world- which is a productive outcome. Jdaitawi (2019) affirmed that in a flipped classroom, students use online instructional clips and text materials whenever it is most convenient for them to prepare their course materials before class. Also, a flipped classroom, which is an instrumentality of technology helps to achieve learning outcomes faster and easier. With the flipped classroom model, lectures are replaced with group projects and independent study of the course contents (Chen, Wang, Kinshuk, & Chen, 2014; Lai & Hwang, 2016).

A germane reason for teaching is to promote active learning, and this is achievable via a technologically-driven flipped classroom. Participatory learning activities involve the teacher and students discussing, arguing, presenting, and modelling the lesson's material (Estes, Ingram and Liu, 2014). This develops

students' independent, creative and problem-solving skills. To strengthen their post-class activities, students in flipped classrooms control what they learn by researching and critically thinking about their course content. Similarly, with the use of flipped classrooms, educators may maximise both teacher and student feedback while also promoting self-study, increasing student engagement, and stimulating cooperation among students.

Online Learning and Technological Tool for Improving Teaching and Learning outcome

Electronic learning or “e-learning” as it is commonly known, is the process of supporting and facilitating learning and education through the use of digital technology mostly the internet. Similarly, the terms web-based instruction, internet-based education, e-learning, shared learning, digital learning and virtual learning are all used to describe online learning. A wide variety of computer-based learning platforms, including multimedia, educational applications, virtual reality, and the use of new media on stationary and mobile platforms, are all included in online learning, which is not limited to online contexts. For individuals, who for whatever reason, are unable to attend regular classrooms, e-learning offers a flexible and substitute method of learning (Baber, 2020). To buttress this viewpoint, Boyles, (2017) affirmed that, VR allows medical trainees to hone their abilities in a secure setting without having to practise on cadavers of people or animals. In the same vein, Falah, Khan, Alfalah, Chan, Harrison & Charissis (2014) opined that “Medical students may now see anatomy in three dimensions as a result of virtual reality, which offers a far better sense of scale and context than the typically sliced charts and images found in anatomy textbooks.”

Geographical boundaries are eliminated via e-learning, which opens up access to education for a worldwide audience. This can be achieved through synchronous and asynchronous ways. Both synchronous (such as video conferencing, audio channels, and virtual chat rooms) and asynchronous (such as email and discussion boards) techniques can be used for online course participation (Alamri & Tyler-Wood, 2017). In the same vein, pre-recorded videos are used to deliver asynchronous mode and Light-board is used in the studio to record the lecture for video. With Light-board teaching, students can choose how quickly and at what pace they learn. In the synchronous mode, students who had difficulty understanding certain topics in the asynchronous mode get help.

The synchronous and asynchronous techniques are also referred to as blended learning- to facilitate in-person interactions between students and teachers, the blended learning approach establishes a systematic framework for the responsible use of digital tools, online resources, and technology (Bhadri and Patil, 2022). Blended learning offers a dynamic, student-focused learning environment supported by cutting-edge technologies. Also, through group projects, online discussion boards, and other cooperative activities, blended learning frequently promotes student collaboration. In the same vein, students can learn at their own pace and location as a result of blended learning. Outside of scheduled class hours, they can use online resources and do tasks.

Meanwhile, maintaining an edge over rivals and improving accessibility to programmes for an increasingly diverse student body are two benefits of online learning. Further benefits include; increased patronage of online learning, which also

provides the ease of time and location for a larger student body. Further to that, online learning offers a fair and objective level of contact without unjustified bias ravaging society, while also maintaining an intertwined relationship amongst learners. In other words, online learning gives rise to a higher level of trust and bond amongst learners- this is achieved through group discussion. Group discussions, chats and activities can be done on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Google forms (Barr and Miller, 2023). This view was further emphasised by Haleem et al (2022), that “social media has advanced significantly as an educational tool. Social media is widely used by educators and students as a vital component of the e-learning process”. Similarly, with the help of online tools, educators may communicate with fellow educators and share knowledge, making them thrive in the classroom. In the same vein, teachers can present evidence of research-based teaching and learning practices that support student development and administration in their classrooms by integrating social media and technology into their online courses. Furthermore, research has demonstrated that one of the most economical ways to educate developing minds is through the Internet of Things (IoT). Additionally, it is a robot mechanism that incorporates an excellent educational experience for all users (Dreimane & Upenieks, 2022).

However, there are some contrasting views on online learning. Barr and Miller (2013) averred that not every student can benefit from online learning- a feeling of disconnection and loneliness may be felt by some of them when they are studying. In the same vein, developing an online course package is cost-demanding, as it requires a lot of resources both human and material- particularly at the beginning. Eventually, it becomes cost effective as cost reduction via economies of scale is achieved- this is evident through increased student enrolment as courses become popular and widely known and elimination of facility-usage cost. This stance was corroborated by Camilleri & Camulleri (2017), Beardsley, Albo, Aragon, & Hernandez Leo (2021), who opined that e-learning helps in cost reduction.

Furthermore, the fact that there are few opportunities to establish trust makes creating an online environment more challenging. Moreso, student actions might fail to exhibit moral traits like transparency, trustworthiness, and dependability. This perspective is supported by the notion that there are greater possibilities for deception and cheating. In the same vein, the quality of education offered online, compared to conventional learning institutions, is considered ineffective. An addendum to this is the very fact that online teaching and learning is tasking and demanding, and could lead to burnout on the part of teachers and learners (Hogan and Knight, 2007). A significant factor in burnout is the possibility of educators working beyond regular business hours. Efficient time management can sometimes provide difficulties for students. Further to that, the speed and intricacy of conversations held in person may be absent from correspondence via the Internet. There is a chance of misconceptions, and it could be difficult to determine the understanding level of learners.

In developing parts of the world, some students are not computer savvy hence, militating against the success of online courses. This is because digital skills include virtual interaction and collaborative abilities as well as the ability to use electronic devices for data and information creation, processing, searching, and manipulation (Carretero, Vuorikari, Punie, 2017). For collaboration, evaluations, and content delivery,

educators must get acquainted with a variety of internet resources and platforms. These tools can have their complexities, and regular upgrades might necessitate continual adaptation. In addition to this, technical problems like slow internet connectivity, bugs in programmes, or hardware breakdowns can affect learners as well as educators.

Distance Learning and Technology

Martin, Sun, and Westine (2020) averred that with the advent of the internet, distance learning has transitioned from in-person to virtual spaces. In furtherance to this argument, Viscione and D'elia (2019) presented a historical overview of the generations of distance learning. In the first generation, the mode of communication was majorly paper. Compiling, editing, and returning assessment results was largely paper-based. The second generation is the age of multimedia- television, radio, phone, and fax are examples of audio and video technologies used in the multimedia approach. The third generation synchronises exchanges through the use of telecommunications technology. The fourth generation draws heavily from the constructivist school of thought. A flexible learning approach that enables online sharing of educational resources. The fifth generation is a sophisticated and adaptive approach to learning that uses internet access as an exclusive unique channel that seeks to improve the characteristics of the fourth generation.

Additionally, words used to describe distance education are e-learning and online learning, this agrees with the view of Kara (2020) who affirmed that it is a two-sided relationship between the learners and facilitators that engenders effective teaching and learning process. Via distance learning, time and space limitations are eliminated (Liu, 2012) - students and teachers don't need to be present in a single physical environment. Further to this, Kostopoulos & Kotsiantis (2022) affirmed that students take real-world experience to their homes. As a result, people from all over the world can take part in the same classes without having to change locations. Increased successful completion of degree rates, enhanced student access, and the attractiveness of online learning to unconventional students are just a few of the rationales behind distance-learning programmes.

With the fusion of technology and distance learning, adaptive learning technology is explored- adaptive educational platforms tailor educational experiences according to each student's achievement and advancement. It also helps students to learn at their own pace (Rose and Iloanya, 2016). A key requirement for effective open and distance learning is the adoption of new communication tools that are intended to give students fluid information and extremely participatory environments. Further to that, students can study courses more interestingly and engagingly through immersive experiences offered by Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies. Virtual reality (VR) is defined by Inoue (2012) as "an interactive computer-based application that provides a synthetic digital environment – thus, virtual reality provides a way to simulate environments, objects, actions, and processes." Virtual Reality in distance learning can serve purposes like class presentations, slides and videos- it uses computer technology to provide digital experiences that are manually difficult to produce. In essence, it is an actual simulator that allows users to behave and react genuinely by placing them in a setting that represents possibly real occurrences (Slater & Sanchez,

2016). Soliman et al (2021) viewed VR as a computer-simulated world that allows the user to communicate and adjust their perspective through a variety of sensory data that is transmitted to the brain. This implies that it presents scenarios to the user, which are afterward interpreted in a more meaningful way. To further explain this, foreign language students can engage the instrumentality of VR to learn, this is achieved by engaging students in interactions with native speakers using a 3D virtual world- this helps to bridge the communication gap (Boylse, 2017).

Virtual reality can be used to close the knowledge gap between practical and theoretical learning (Dubovi, Levy and Dagan, 2017). Also, Virtual reality (VR) holds great potential as an immersive and interactive tool to improve distance learning (Harfouche & Nahkle, 2020). VR provides a learner-friendly environment, which makes it possible for socialization, in these settings, individuals can carry out certain tasks and engage with others (Liou, 2012), (Huang, Liaw & Lai, 2013). Chang, Hsu, Kuo, & Jong (2019) averred that VR also creates a fun-filled environment suitable for learning. Various functionalities of VR which are expressed through virtual communication help to fortify interactions among students. In the same vein, VR in distance learning helps students sharpen their creativity skills. Users can practise and improve their interpersonal abilities in a secure setting without being nervous in virtual reality surroundings (Howard & Gutworth, 2020). In other words, virtual reality prompts students to engage in more in-depth dialogue, investigation, and curiosity-driven learning. AR and VR could be used to address the problems associated with distance learning through the simulation of real-life scenarios to enhance learning.

A practical example of this is the use of AR to train and evaluate medical students. In using a surgical dummy, ProMIS is an augmented reality video simulator that joins labels and internal organs on a video feed to teach and assess students- through this, students have a near-reality experience of what an internal organ looks like. In connection with that, the virtual laboratory can be created for science practical, although this cannot effectively replace physical ones, however, it would help in effective time management and decongestion of physical laboratories (Potkonjak, Gardner, Callaghan, Mattila, Guetl, Petrović, & Jovanović, 2016; Frank and Kapila, 2017; Ananda Maiti, Smith, Maxwell & Kist, 2018). Also, Augmented Reality (AR) software is typically accessible through mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets. They utilise built-in cameras, GPS sensors, and Internet connectivity to integrate ever-changing, context-aware, and interactive digital information into real-world surroundings (Chiang, Lee, Yang & Liang, 2014). Since learning has become what students can relate to through AR, it has now translated into a motivating factor for learners, which spurs them into active learning.

Also, since distance learning is conducted online, precautions for cyber-security are essential to safeguard confidential information and maintain a safe learning environment. A wide range of activities falls under the umbrella of cyber-security operations, including digital forensics, crisis management, hacking, online threat intelligence, cyber defence, and offensive operations carried out by authorised government agencies (Wagner & Alharthi, 2023). They further posited that augmented reality and cyber-security have been fused to protect internet users, tasks ranging from phishing to ransomware, WiFi security, password creation, data protection, file backups, and social media best practices—all based on Technology Threat Avoidance

Theory (TTAT)—CybAR is an Augmented Reality application that challenges and engages users. Additionally, cloud-based applications allow easy accessibility from multiple places and do away with the necessity for storage space by facilitating the sharing, collaboration, and storing of educational content.

Through technologically embedded distance learning, learner interaction is fostered and developed. Through efficient use of technology, interactions can be enhanced in online distance learning (ODL) and assist in ensuring learning is effective which is the desired learning outcome (Mathew and Iloanya, 2016). Further to that, distance learning has paved the way for learning new abilities, which has been enhanced by the use of "game mechanics" in learning tasks, such as emblems, difficulties, levels, and points. Jeidi, Sehweil and Al-Qasim (2014) affirmed that game mechanics (Gamification) critically considers students' learning objectives- which further helps to factor in the mode of teaching them. A few examples of gaming applications that fosters online learning are Duolingo, Quizzes and Kahoot. If done properly, learning to use gamification in both holistic technology integration and traditional distant learning models could have a significant positive impact on learning environments.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations for the attainment of effective learning outcomes through technology:

1. Facilitators should be encouraged to adopt the use of technology in their teaching methodology. In addition to this, consideration should be given to students' needs first. Educational resources should be selected based on their interests, skills, and preferences. Technology ought to be used as a tool to support education, not a distraction.
2. Lecturers and teachers in higher institutions and secondary schools should set precise goals and objectives for the teaching and learning process before introducing technology.
3. Furthermore, facilitators should create time for continuous professional development to stay current with emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches.
4. In addition to that, facilitators should examine engaging resources, experiments, and instructional technological tools that can help make difficult ideas more approachable and real for students.
5. Students should be sensitized about appropriate technology use and internet safety. This would assist them in comprehending the moral obligations and issues related to using technology.

Conclusion

Technology is germane in the attainment of effective learning outcomes. With the adoption of more modern and recent technology, such as virtual and augmented realities, the teaching and learning process has become easy. Also, with the adoption of e-learning, barriers to learning have been eliminated. Further to that, the adoption of technology would contribute to learning outcomes across all fields of learning. Students

in educational lines such as medicine, language, administration, history and arts can take full advantage of technological tools to further deepen and widen their learning scope.

Finally, the inclusion of technology in the teaching and learning process would help to develop the creative and critical thinking skills of students. This helps to help them fit effectively into the wider society.

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